

DRAGON Statistical Analysis Plan

As the primary outcome of the DRAGON (Diagnostic Report Analysis: General Optimization of NLP) study, we statistically compare the downstream performance of models pretrained with different pretraining strategies. The pretraining strategies we compare are domain-specific pretraining (using diagnostic reports), general-domain pretraining (using Wikipedia, books, etc.), and mixed-domain pretraining (general-domain followed by domain-specific pretraining). Performance is evaluated by calculating the test set performance across each architecture, each downstream task, and each fine-tuning training run. For each pretraining configuration, multiple architectures are pretrained and evaluated, and results are pooled together to compare the pretraining strategies. Downstream performance for each task is determined by fine-tuning the pretrained model using the training set of the downstream task and calculating the performance on the test set of the downstream task. This fine-tuning step is performed five times, where the training set is a different 80% of the development dataset each run.

Statistical tests are reserved for four primary outcomes only, in compliance with expert guidelines (1). To maintain the type I error while investigating multiple comparisons, all study objectives are prespecified in a hierarchical family and tested accordingly (2).

Figure 1 shows the statistical tests for the four primary outcomes:

- 1A. Is domain-specific pretraining superior to general-domain pretraining?
- 1B. Is mixed-domain pretraining superior to general-domain pretraining?
- 2A. Is domain-specific pretraining superior to mixed-domain pretraining?
- 2B. Is mixed-domain pretraining superior to domain-specific pretraining?

Multiplicity is corrected for at each stage using the Holm–Bonferroni method, considering a base alpha value of 0.05.

Figure 1: Flowchart illustrating the strategic plan to test the study objectives, while maintaining the type I error rate. Significance thresholds used for family 1A and 1B are adjusted using the Holm–Bonferroni method, considering a base alpha value of 0.05. If the null hypothesis for family 1A is rejected, but that of family 1B is not rejected, then we move on to testing family 2A with an alpha value of 0.025 but do not test family 2B. Conversely, if the null hypothesis for family 1B is rejected but that of family 1A is not rejected, then we move on to testing family 2B with an alpha value of 0.025, but do not test family 2A. If the null hypotheses for both family 1A and 1B are rejected, then we move on to testing both family 2A and 2B, where the significance threshold is once again adjusted using the Holm–Bonferroni method considering a base alpha value of 0.05. If neither family 1A nor 1B are rejected, neither family 2A nor 2B will be tested.

Calculation of P Values

The primary endpoints of this study are compared using the permutation test. The efficacy of each pretraining approach is defined by the performance observed for each of the 28 tasks, with each of the five network architectures, across five fine-tuning runs (the tasks and architectures are listed below). This results in $28 \cdot 5 \cdot 5 = 700$ independent training runs and performance metrics per pretraining configuration. Performance metrics are comparable between architectures and fine-tuning runs, but not between tasks. To isolate the effect of pretraining from the effect of the architecture, we only compare performance metrics from the same architecture. As such, in $5 \times 28 = 140$ groups, the five performance metrics from the five fine-tuning runs of the baseline configuration are compared with the five performance metrics from the five fine-tuning runs of the alternative configuration. We permute the performance metrics within each of these 140 groups to obtain the null distribution of no performance difference.

The test statistic for the permutation test is the mean order-AUC across all groups, following (3):

$$S = \frac{1}{140} \sum_{i=1}^{28} \sum_{j=1}^5 \text{AUC}\{S_{ij,baseline}, S_{ij,alternative}\}$$

Where $S_{ij,baseline}$ and $S_{ij,alternative}$ each denote a set of five performance metrics, for the baseline and alternative configuration, respectively.

The P value for superiority in the context of a permutation test can be calculated directly from the null distribution. The null distribution is constructed as follows: calculate the test statistic for the observed data; randomly permute the performance metrics between modalities (baseline and alternative configurations) and recalculate the test statistic; repeat permutations and recalculation of the test statistic a large number of times (100,000) to generate a distribution under the null hypothesis. The P value is then calculated as the proportion of permuted statistics that are equal to or more extreme than the observed statistic:

$$p = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbb{1}\{S_i \geq S_o\}$$

Where $\mathbb{1}\{S_i \geq S_o\}$ equals 1 if the statistic (S_i) is equal to or more extreme than the observed statistic (S_o) in iteration i of the permutation test, or 0 otherwise. N is the number of permutation test iterations.

Architectures and tasks

The following five architectures are included:

1. Dutch BERT (HuggingFace: GroNLP/bert-base-dutch-cased)
2. Multi-lingual RoBERTa base (HuggingFace: xlm-roberta-base)
3. Multi-lingual RoBERTa large (HuggingFace: xlm-roberta-large)
4. English Longformer base (HuggingFace: allenai/longformer-base-4096)
5. English Longformer large (HuggingFace: allenai/longformer-large-4096)

The following 28 tasks are used to evaluate model performance:

1. Adhesion presence
2. Pulmonary nodule presence
3. Kidney abnormality identification
4. Skin histopathology case selection
5. RECIST timeline
6. Histopathology cancer origin
7. Pulmonary nodule size presence

8. Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma size presence
9. Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma diagnosis
10. Prostate radiology suspicious lesions
11. Prostate histopathology significant cancers
12. Histopathology sample origin
13. Histopathology sample type
14. Entailment diagnostic sentences
15. Colon histopathology diagnosis
16. RECIST lesion size presence
17. Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma attributes
18. Hip Kellgren-Lawrence scoring
19. Prostate volume extraction
20. Prostate specific antigen extraction
21. Prostate specific antigen density extraction
22. Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma size measurement
23. Pulmonary nodule size measurement
24. RECIST lesion size measurement
25. Anonymization
26. Medical terminology recognition
27. Prostate biopsy sampling
28. Skin histopathology diagnosis

References:

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